

Does Energy Discreteness Follow Directly From the Maxwell-Boltzmann Probability?

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In Newtonian mechanics there exists a continuous x i.e. for a conservative force: $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ with x taking any value. This is associated with the idea of $dx \rightarrow 0$. As a result one may choose an x and $x+dx$ with $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $v(x)$ and $v(x+dx)$ become arbitrarily close in value. It is almost as if their identities merge.

In (1) entropy and average energy are calculated using the Maxwell-Boltzmann MB factor $\exp(-e/T)$ and a continuous energy. The results $E = NT$ ($k=1$) and $S = -\ln(T/T_0)$ with T_0 being an integration constant show that one must have $T > T_0$ because $T \rightarrow 0$ does not lead to $S \rightarrow 0$. Thus there is a problem if one uses continuous energy. In other words continuous energy is rejected. (1) then considers an equally spaced energy i.e. $e = bn$, $n=0,1,2,3 \dots$ and calculates energy and entropy again. In this case $S \rightarrow 0$ as $T \rightarrow 0$. Thus (1) concludes that it is entropy which leads to the discretization of energy

In this note we try to argue that discretization of energy is already implied by the MB factor. The MB factor $\exp(-\text{energy}/T)$ where T is a math parameter called temperature represents a probability. In other words, different energies have different probabilities i.e. one must distinguish between them. Having two energy values merge is a problem now because one has a second parameter T which may also go to zero i.e. $e_2 - e_1 \rightarrow 0$ and $T \rightarrow 0$ leads to trouble because $\exp(-e_2/T)$ does not tend to zero as it should if $e_1 = 0$.

We argue that the underlying reason for e_1 and e_2 being discretely different is that one cannot use the probability/ T formalism i.e. MB factor unless interactions occur. We argue that such two body interactions cannot ultimately transfer or remove a $de \rightarrow 0$ and keep e_1 and e_2 distinct. In other words the interaction/collision is ultimately linked to a finite energy transfer even though $T \rightarrow 0$.

As a result energy should be discretized in an equilibrium scenario. This argument does not make use of entropy explicitly although implicitly having $\exp(-e_2/T) \rightarrow 0$ as $T \rightarrow 0$ (say for a 2 level system) means that the particle is in state e_1 which may be associated with an entropy of 0 if one ignores internal features of this state. We also note that the continuous energy result $E = NT$, and not just the entropy, leads to trouble because as T becomes extremely tiny E which is an average of say e_1 and e_2 with $e_1 = 0$ as an example approaches T in magnitude. The smaller T becomes the smaller e_2 becomes which e_2 and e_1 no longer have separate identities, but in such a case one does not have an equilibrium scenario either. In other words $\exp(-e/T)$ implies interactions between distinguishable states with respect to energy.

Entropy and $T \rightarrow 0$

Reference (1) focuses on using the MB factor $\exp(-e/T)$ to calculate E_{average} and S (entropy) for both continuous and discrete energy level scenarios.

The continuous energy approach leads to:

$$E_{\text{ave}} = \left\{ \sum_i e_i \exp(-e_i/T) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \right\} = (k_B) T$$

and $S = \int dT \frac{1}{T} dE/dT = -k_B \ln(T/T_0)$

One may see that S already has a problem because $T \rightarrow 0$ does not lead to $S \rightarrow 0$. Thus (1) rejects the idea of continuous energy and redoes the calculation assuming $e = b n$ where b is a constant and $n = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots$

Using a discrete energy one obtains an expression for S such that $T \rightarrow 0$ means $S \rightarrow 0$. Thus (1) concludes that entropy arguments lead to energy changing by discrete amounts.

Derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Using Reaction Balance

The MB distribution may be derived using reaction balance (i.e. a time reversal balance of two body elastic scattering):

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1b)) and linking to ((1a)) with a constant $1/T$ yields:

$$n(e_1) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-e_1/T) \quad ((2))$$

We wish to stress that the above procedure only applies if an interaction occurs. In such a case one has two sets of information, namely energy $e(i)$ and probability to have an $e(i)$ i.e. $n(e(i))$. One then suggests that these two seemingly different pieces of information should in fact be linked to each other so that they are not independent. The parameter T is used to describe the average energy in the system which is a constraint.

Mathematically one may write similar equations for the case of no reaction i.e.:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_1 + e_2 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_1)n(e_2) \quad ((3b))$$

In such a case e_1 and $n(e_1)$ are two pieces of information, but are completely independent. Thus it does not make sense to take \ln of ((3b)) and link it with ((3a)). There is no reaction to link the two pieces of information so create one piece of information given the T constraint. Thus equilibrium reduces information in the system by forcing the $n(e(i))$'s to adjust so that they are simple functions of $e(i)$ and not independent of $e(i)$ i.e. two pieces of information become one.

What then does it mean to take the limit $T \rightarrow 0$? We suggest that for a two level system as an example one tries to push as much probability into level 1 and as little as possible into level 2. E_1 and e_2 , however, must be distinct because an interaction is occurring in the case of T being present even if it becomes tiny. As a result T must become tiny with e_2 remaining distinguishable or discrete i.e.

The probabilities for a two level system are: $1 - \exp(-e_2/T)$ and $\exp(-e_2/T)$.

If $T \rightarrow 0$ and $e_1 = 0$ then e_2 cannot approach 0 in order to have $\exp(-e_2/T) \rightarrow 0$.

If $T \rightarrow 0$ and $e_1 = b = \text{finite value}$, then e_2 cannot be b as well because the two states would not be distinguishable.

Thus we argue that it is distinguishability or two pieces of independent information one being e_1 and the other e_2 which is essential. Otherwise one could not have a reaction and could not use T (temperature) in the first place.

How does this differ from Newtonian mechanics for which x and $x+dx$ and $v(x)$ and $v(x+dx)$ may be arbitrarily close in value? Why does one not distinguish the two in that case and argue for discreteness of energy? We argue that $V(x)$, the potential, allows for the two states to be distinguished. In other words Newtonian mechanics is governed by $V(x)$ i.e. $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2 = E - V(x)$. If one does not have constant potential, then $V(x)$ and $V(x+dx)$ are linked to different states. In the MB gas there does not need to be a potential. Thus if e_1 and e_2 become arbitrarily close to each other there is nothing to distinguish between the two and one does not have an interaction. The interaction between e_1 and e_2 suggests that they must be different i.e. have a finite gap linked to a minimal energy transfer. In other words the interaction (i.e. collision) does not move smoothly to 0 as $T \rightarrow 0$.

Problem with $E = N(k_B) T$ [$k_B = \text{Boltzmann constant}$]

For $T \rightarrow 0$ $E = N(k_B) T$ suggests that average energy $\rightarrow 0$. This means that for a two level system e_1 and e_2 , $e_1 \rightarrow 0$, but $e_2 \exp(-e_2/T)$ cannot have $e_2 \rightarrow 0$ because $\exp(-e_2/T)$ would be undefined as $T \rightarrow 0$. Thus the continuous energy result also suggests that e_2 must be a finite value greater than e_1 . Given that there is discreteness in energy levels one may even question whether $e_1 = 0$ holds. For example in quantum mechanics there is a minimum ground state energy value.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that discreteness of energy levels in a statistical mechanical equilibrium, as employed by Planck, seems to follow directly from the form of the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$ which in turn is linked to interactions e.g. two body collisions in a gas (gas particle with gas particle or gas particle with wall particle). We further argue that in a collision $e(\text{before})$ and $e(\text{after})$ must be distinguishable states in terms of energy, otherwise an interaction does not occur and one cannot use T (temperature). This interaction must deliver or remove a finite amount of energy from $e(\text{before})$ in order to make it distinguishable from $e(\text{after})$. This finite amount cannot tend to 0. Thus even if $T \rightarrow 0$, e_2 in a two level system must be separated in value from e_1 by a finite value. Thus we argue that even though one may argue for discrete energy levels by computing entropy and taking the $T \rightarrow 0$ limit, the MB factor already leads to this conclusion in particular because there must be an interaction between two states which ensures that they remain distinguishable. This we argue is the basis for discrete energy.

References

1. Benguigui, L. The Different Paths to Entropy (2008 or later)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1209.2268.pdf>